

Studies on the Citrate Complex of Calcium

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The citrate complex of calcium has been investigated by the pH titration method in the pH range of 7.1 to 7.25. The equilibrium constant of the reaction,

is 2.66×10^3 .

Hastings and collaborators (*J. Biol. Chem.*, 1934, **107**, 351) determined the stability constant of the calcium citrate chelate by the biological assay method and found the equilibrium constant to be 1.585×10^3 . They could not detect the existence of complexes with more than one ligand.

From conductance and transport measurements Henning *et al.* (*Z. Kinderh.*, 1951, **69**, 55) observed reaction between Ca^{2+} and citrate ion to form CaCit^{-} , independent of pH.

Schubert and Lindenbaum (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1952, **74**, 3529) studied the complex formation between Ca^{2+} and a series of organic acids. These complexes are of 1 : 1 type. The formation constant of calcium citrate complex is found to be 1.445×10^3 .

EXPERIMENTAL

A very pure sample of calcium carbonate was added in excess to *M/5* perchloric acid solution (125 c.c.) so that some solid was left undissolved. The solution was boiled to remove CO_2 present, cooled, and left for about 4 hours. It was then filtered to a 250 c.c. measuring flask and diluted to the mark. The solution was estimated for calcium content by oxalate method and found to contain *M/20* calcium perchlorate.

Experiment I.—Curve A (Fig. 1) represents the results obtained by titrating 200 c.c. of a solution containing 0.025 g. mole of citric acid and curve B represents the results obtained by titrating 0.025 g. mole of citric acid and 0.0025 g. mole of calcium perchlorate against *N-NaOH* at 33°.

Experiment II.—Curve A (Fig. 2) represents the results obtained by titrating 100 c.c. of a solution containing 0.025 g. mole of sodium perchlorate and curve B represents that of another solution containing 0.025 g. mole of sodium perchlorate and 0.00125 g. mole of calcium perchlorate against 0.1 *M* sodium citrate at 33°.

DISCUSSION

In experiment (I) the ρH of the system B is little lower than that of the system A. The horizontal distance between the two curves increases in the beginning, then decreases, and finally becomes negligible after ρH 6.0. The small horizontal distance between the two curves, especially the negligible distance at the neutralisation point of the citric acid, indicates that no acid is liberated. The low ρH in the system B may be ascribed to removal of citrate ligand from the solution by calcium ions due to complex formation.

FIG. 1

In experiment (II) the ρH of the system (B), which contains calcium, is lower than that of the other system. This is probably due to the removal of citrate ion from the solution by the calcium ion on account of formation of the complex. The added citrate ion is most probably removed partially from the solution and hence the ρH of the system does not rise as rapidly as found in curve A.

The ρH of the solution rises only after the addition of very nearly one g. mole of sodium citrate per g. mole of calcium perchlorate. This indicates the formation of a very stable 1 : 1 complex.

FIG. 2

Calculation of the Equilibrium Constant

Due to the reaction of citrate ion and Ca^{2+} , no acid is liberated. Hence the complex would be CaCit^- . In experiment (II) the reaction may be represented by equation (1) and the equilibrium constant by equation (1-1).

where $[\text{CaCit}^-]$, $[\text{Ca}^{2+}]$, and $[\text{Cit}^{3-}]$ represent the molar concentration of CaCit^- complex, calcium ion, and free citrate ion respectively.

Let A and B be the two points on the same pH axis on curves A and B respectively. Let $[\text{Ct}]_A$, $[\text{Cit}^{3-}]_A$, $[\text{Ct}]_B$, $[\text{Cit}^{3-}]_B$, and $[\text{Ca}(\text{ClO}_4)_2]$ represent the molar concentration of total citrate at A, free citrate at A, total citrate at B, and free citrate ion at B, and calcium perchlorate respectively.

It is assumed that Ca^{2+} is not hydrolysed at pH 7.1 to 7.3. Hence the pH of the solution depends on the concentration of citrate ion.

It is further assumed that at the same pH, the citrate ion concentration in the systems A and B is the same. Hence the free citrate ion concentration at A and B is equal to $[\text{Cit}^{3-}]_A$.

$$\text{Total citrate at A} = [\text{Ct}]_A = [\text{Cit}^{3-}]_A \quad \dots (2)$$

$$\text{Total citrate at B} = [\text{Ct}]_B = [\text{Cit}^{3-}]_A + [\text{CaCit}^-] \quad \dots (2-1)$$

$$\text{Hence } [\text{CaCit}^-] = [\text{Ct}]_B - [\text{Ct}]_A \quad \dots (2-2)$$

$[\text{Ca}(\text{ClO}_4)_2]$ is calculated from the g.moles of calcium perchlorate taken and the total volume of the solution $[\text{Ct}]_A$ and $[\text{Ct}]_B$ is calculated from g.moles of sodium citrate added and volume of the solution at A and B respectively.

$[\text{Ca}^{2+}]$ can be calculated by subtracting $[\text{CaCit}^-]$ from $[\text{Ca}(\text{ClO}_4)_2]$.

TABLE I

pH.	$[\text{Cit}^{3-}] \times 10^4$.	$[\text{Ct}]_B \times 10^3$.	$[\text{Ca}(\text{ClO}_4)_2] \times 10^2$.	$[\text{CaCit}^-] \times 10^2$.	$[\text{Ca}^{2+}] \times 10^2$.	$K \times 10^{-2}$.
7.17	0.9988	1.380	1.233	1.281	11.05	1.160
7.22	2.990	2.334	1.221	2.045	10.17	0.723
7.23	3.985	3.482	1.209	3.084	9.01	0.8592
7.24	3.985	3.661	1.204	3.263	8.78	0.9326
7.24	3.985	3.847	1.201	3.449	8.56	1.011
7.25	3.985	5.661	1.180	5.263	6.54	2.018
7.25	3.985	5.927	1.176	5.529	6.23	2.227
7.25	3.985	6.542	1.168	6.144	5.54	2.784
7.25	3.985	7.408	1.157	7.010	4.56	3.858
7.25	3.985	8.256	1.147	7.858	3.61	5.463

The equilibrium constant K is calculated at different pH values by equation (1-1). The values are tabulated in Table I. The mean value of K is found to be 2.66×10^2 . This is in good

agreement with the value obtained by Schubert and Hindenbaum (*loc. cit.*) and also with that obtained by Hastings *et al.* (*loc. cit.*).

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